

* Encoding: UTF-8.

Exemplary SPSS Syntax for steps of the one-with-many (OWM) design:

1. Creating variables centred on the grand mean ($_c$)

```
COMPUTE Trust_c=Trust - Trust_mean.  
EXECUTE.
```

2. Creating variables at the between-dyad level ($_b$) - the average for focal persons

```
AGGREGATE  
/OUTFILE=* MODE=ADDVARIABLES  
/BREAK=D_ID  
/Trust_b=MEAN(Trust_c).
```

3. Creating variables at the within_dyad level ($_w$) - the individual values for each dyad members

```
COMPUTE Trust_w=Trust_c - Trust_b.  
EXECUTE.
```

4. Exemplary Syntax used for variance partitioning

```
MIXED  
Communication BY Role WITH Doctor Patient  
/FIXED = Doctor Patient | NOINT  
/PRINT = SOLUTION TESTCOV  
/RANDOM Doctor Patient | SUBJECT(D_ID) COVTYPE(UNR)  
/REPEATED = Role | SUBJECT(D_ID *Dyad_ID) COVTYPE(UNR).
```

5. Exemplary Syntax used for estimating the tested association

```
MIXED  
Satisfaction BY Role WITH Doctor Patient Trust_b Trust_w  
/FIXED = Doctor Patient Doctor*Trust_b Doctor*Trust_w Patient*Trust_b Patient*Trust_w  
| NOINT  
/PRINT = SOLUTION TESTCOV  
/RANDOM Doctor Patient | SUBJECT(D_ID) COVTYPE(UNR)  
/REPEATED = Role | SUBJECT(D_ID *Dyad_ID) COVTYPE(UNR).
```

6. Exemplary Syntax used for estimating the tested association effect sizes by incorporating a control variable in the model

MIXED

Trust BY Role WITH Doctor Patient BenevolenceParticular_b BenevolenceParticular_w
Propensity_c

/FIXED = Doctor Patient Patient*BenevolenceParticular_b

Patient*BenevolenceParticular_w Patient*Propensity_c| NOINT

/PRINT = SOLUTION TESTCOV

/RANDOM Doctor Patient | SUBJECT(D_ID) COVTYPE(UNR)

/REPEATED = Role | SUBJECT(D_ID *Dyad_ID) COVTYPE(UNR).